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ACTIVE INTERFACES – Holistic strategy to simplify standards, assessments and certification for building integrated photovoltaics

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Significance of prevailing regulations, standards and labels for the deployment of BIPV

Report 3/3

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1 Introduction

1.1 Context

«Active Interfaces» (AI) explores holistic operational strategies overcoming obstacles for large-scale advanced PV integration into urban renewal and building renovation processes. «Active Interfaces» aims to foster widespread deployment of building integrated PV solutions (BIPV). To this end, AI investigates the potential for deploying BIPV-solutions as well as the significance and relevance of existing and of future expected framework conditions, of possible drivers and obstacles regarding BIPV deployment as well as the possibilities to overcome existing BIPV barriers and to foster BIPV deployment.

Within «Active Interfaces», BIPV-solutions will be developed and optimized for archetypal buildings and case studies. Resulting impacts of BIPV-solutions on energy generation and consumption, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, costs and economic viability will be assessed and compared with renewal and renovation solutions not applying BIPV solutions.

In Switzerland as well as in the international context there is a lack of common calculation, assessment and evaluation methods applicable in the planning, calculation design and evaluation of BIPV solutions although methodological basics and approaches have been worked out for numerous research projects as well as for the development of PV-related standards and labels. It is suspected that this situation hampers widespread deployment of PV/BIPV. On that basis, barriers as well as effects of regulations, standards and labels fostering BIPV-deployment are subsequently identified and qualitatively assessed with respect to their relevance regarding BIPV deployment. The chapters comprise the Swiss situation, which is assessed in detail. Additionally the corresponding regulations and programs on the level of the European Union, in Germany and in Austria are briefly investigated and summarized.

The present Report 3 completes the contributions of econcept in Project 04 of Active Interfaces. Existing reports of econcept for Active Interfaces:

Report 1: «Common methodological framework to assess energy, climate and economic impacts of BIPV», 30.6. 2016

Report 2: «Energy-policy analysis», 30.6. 2016

1.2 Goals

The present report 3 aims to identify regulations, standards and labels which are relevant for PV and BIPV having fostering or hampering effects on PV/BIPV deployment.

The report was elaborated within Project 04 of Active Interfaces in two steps. In the first step for the Swiss situation which was then supplemented by the situation on the EU level as well as in Germany and Austria, respectively. It is based on the collection and analysis of legal provisions, Swiss standards and labels as well as on related Swiss literature in the

realm of PV/BIPV. The analysis of the federal energy law and the corresponding ordinances relies on the new proposition which has been approved by the Swiss voters on May 21st 2017.

The present report was elaborated by econcept. The association Swissolar (David Stickelberger) contributed to the paper with important feedbacks, adding experiences from political discussions on PV and BIPV deployment on the federal, cantonal and communal level in Switzerland as well as with current experiences in deploying PV/BIPV installations on buildings in Switzerland. HSLU (Christian Roeske and Stephen Wittkopf) suggested reviews of relevant German and Austrian policies and corresponding regulations and standards. They provided feedbacks to a draft report and delivered technical and scientific inputs.

1.3 Research questions

Research questions for the investigation of hindering as well as fostering impacts of prevailing regulations, guidelines, standards and labels on BIPV-deployment:

- Which regulations, guidelines, standards and labels have an impact on the deployment of BIPV and on the energy and GHG related assessment of BIPV- and PV-solutions in Switzerland? Thereby, a special focus lies on current assessment or conversion factors, system boundaries, allocation rules, regulatory requirements.
- What is the impact of the identified BIPV- and PV-related regulations, guidelines, standards and labels on BIPV-deployment?
- Which energy related regulations and evaluation procedures regarding BIPV and PV have been established on the level of provisions of the European Union and in Germany and Austria?
- Which conclusions and recommendations can be made for the further development of the framework conditions regarding BIPV deployment?

2 BIPV-relevant regulations, standards and labels

In a first step, the investigation of BIPV-relevant framework conditions like regulations, guidelines, standards and labels is carried out for Switzerland. In a subsequent step, the situation in the countries surrounding Switzerland is investigated (mainly the regulations of the European «Energy Performance of Buildings Directive» EPBD and the «Energy Efficiency Directive»). Since the Swiss federal energy law (EnG) assigns the competence regarding energy policy for the building sector to the cantons, the cantonal energy laws and corresponding energy ordinances would have to be investigated in addition to federal regulations. The cantons have harmonized cantonal subsidy programs for energy related building measures (HFM 2015) as well as the further development of their energy laws (MuKE 2014). Hence, the subsequent investigations are based on the federal framework conditions like the Swiss energy law (EnG), Swiss labels and standards (the Minergie labels and the Plusenergie-Haus) and the above mentioned harmonized cantonal regulations according to MuKE 2014, but not on the particular cantonal energy laws and subsidy programs.

Technical guidelines and regulations are not investigated here since the project partner from SUPSI (Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana) is doing this work within «Active Interfaces».

2.1 Evaluated Swiss regulations, guidelines, standards and labels

The analysis and evaluation of the Swiss situation encompasses the following regulations, standards and labels:

- Model rules for the cantonal energy policy in the building sector («Mustervorschriften der Kantone im Energiebereich MuKE 2014»; EnFK 2014)
- (New) Swiss energy law (Energiegesetz des Bundes, EnG 2017, proposition which was accepted in a referendum on May 21st 2017 by the Swiss voting population) and the corresponding federal energy ordinance (Energieverordnung des Bundes, EnV 2017; 1.11. 2017)
- Federal ordinance for energy subsidy programs (EnFV)
- Federal law on spatial planning (RPG) and the federal spatial planning ordinance (RPV)
- Minergie-Standards: Minergie, Minergie-P and Minergie-A (Minergie 2017)
- Plusenergie-Standard (energie-cluster.ch 2017/SIA 2016)
- Energy certificate for buildings (Energieausweis für Gebäude, SIA 2031:2016)
- Amendment of the federal tax law, draft version sent to consultation in February 2017

2.2 Impacts and significance of regulations, guidelines, standards and labels on BIPV deployment

The analysis of the above mentioned regulations, standards and labels bears on identifying barriers to the deployment of BIPV as well as existing framework conditions fostering BIPV in the case of building construction or renovation.

Existing subsidy programs like feed-in remuneration (KEV/EV) or investment contributions/one-off fee payment (Einmalvergütung) are not assessed on a quantitative monetary basis but rather with a view on the subsidy logic and subsidy conditions.

2.2.1 PV versus BIPV

«Active Interfaces» focusses on building integrated PV solutions (BIPV). Building integrated photovoltaics are multifunctional photovoltaic panels that are used to replace on the one hand conventional building elements in parts of the building envelope such as the roof or the façade and on the other hand they generate electricity. The general term photovoltaics (PV) applies rather to a photovoltaic system added onto the building, most often onto the roof, without replacing conventional building elements. In the following we use the term «PV/BIPV» if an impact holds for PV and BIPV. If the impact is clearly different for PV than for BIPV this is mentioned explicitly.

The local system boundary for on-site electricity production and for the sake of assessments is in the case of BIPV the same as for PV (see econcept, report 1, 30.6. 2016), i.e. surfaces of building attached car parkings may also be used for BIPV.

2.2.2 Overview of significant regulations, standards and labels and the related identified impacts

The following Table 1 summarizes the results from the analyses and evaluations carried out concerning the above mentioned regulations, standards and labels with respect to the following criteria considered to be significant for BIPV deployment:

- Relevant framework conditions and objectives of the particular regulations, standards or labels
- Requirements established within the particular regulations, standards and labels
- System boundaries defined by the regulations, standards and labels
- Allocation rules prescribed by the particular regulations, standards and labels
- Calculation and conversion factors employed. Especially the primary energy factor (PEF) of energy carriers delivered to the building, which indicates besides the energy value of the energy carrier how much energy was used from the source to the delivery of the energy carrier, thereby adding energy content and upstream energy use for processing, transport and distribution of the energy carrier.
- Measures fostering BIPV deployment established by the particular regulations, standards and labels

Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
<p>MuKEn 2014 (basic requirements compulsory) is supposed to be the blueprint for the revision of cantonal energy laws. But the amendment of existing cantonal energy laws by the cantons to comply with MuKEn 2014 (at least basic requirements) is not yet implemented and political acceptance might be uncertain in some of the cantons.</p>	<p>According to MuKEn 2014, the requirements addressing heating energy needs and those addressing on-site electricity generation are defined/appraised separately</p>		
<p>System boundaries: On-site generation of renewable electricity is not taken into account in the calculation of the weighted energy needs for heating and domestic hot water. Consequently, there are no MuKEn standard solutions (SL) with PV/BIPV (except SL 7 for domestic hot water production).</p>			<p>These MuKEn requirements foster primarily high energy efficiency of building envelopes and do not allow for compensating higher energy needs by PV/BIPV deployment to comply with heating energy requirements. MuKEn is still based primarily on the energy needs of a building for space heating and domestic hot water. Current trends tend to focus on the net consumption of non-renewable energy of buildings, taking into account overall energy consumption and the compensation of (non-renewable) energy delivered by on-site energy generation which fosters PV/BIPV deployment.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: The setup of the MuKEn basic energy need regulation is to a certain extent an obstacle to even larger increase of PV/BIPV deployment with a potentially high quantitative relevance.</p>

Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
<p>Calculation and conversion factors: Heated area (m²) is the functional unit for the requirements of MuKE n 2014</p> <p>National (political) conversion factors are used for the different energy carriers (final energy) to appraise the compliance of the weighted energy use with the requirements of MuKE n 2014. Electricity consumption from the grid is weighted by a factor $g_{el} = 2$.</p> <p>This conversion factor does not correspond with life cycle assessed conversion factors for electricity consumed from the grid, taking into account the current mix of electricity consumed in Switzerland which is significantly higher ($g_{el} = 2.68$ for non-renewable primary energy use and 3.14 for total primary energy use) than the national conversion factor of $g_{el} = 2$.</p>			<p>Since on-site generated PV-electricity is not taken into account by MuKE n the choice of the conversion factor for electricity deliveries from the grid made by MuKE n has no effect on PV/BIPV deployment</p>
<p>New buildings: Limit for energy needs MuKE n 2014 limits energy needs for heating and domestic hot water production, ventilation and air conditioning.</p> <p>For new buildings (except residential buildings) which are larger than 1'000 m² electricity demand for lighting is limited.</p>			<p>Since compliance with the limit for heating and domestic hot water energy needs is assessed separately, compensation by on-site electricity generation is not possible, the limit to energy needs does not foster BIPV deployment.</p>
<p>New buildings: Obligation for PV/BIPV New buildings have to generate part of their electricity needs on-site (PV or BIPV)</p>	<p>Integration of PV in façade is allowed.</p> <p>On-site power generation by renewables required: 10W_{peak}/m² heated area, not more than 30kW are required per building.</p> <p>Compensation fee if requirement is not met. MuKE n recommends 1'000 CHF/kW.</p>		<p>This fosters PV/BIPV. The requirements can generally already be met by PV on the roof only and does not require BIPV on the façade.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: The incentive to install PV is quantitatively relevant but it is not demanding enough to have a relevant impact on BIPV deployment.</p>

Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
<p>Existing buildings: Renewable energy use When replacing the heating and hot water production systems, part of the energy needs have to be covered by renewable energy.</p>	<p>When replacing the heating system, at most 90% of heating needs may be covered by non-renewable energy sources.</p> <p>Electricity use for direct heating and hot water production is not allowed anymore and has to be changed until 2025, except if hot water production is made to at least 50% by waste heat or renewable energy.</p> <p>Large existing buildings: For existing buildings (except residential buildings) which are larger than 1'000 m² electricity demand for lighting and ventilation or ventilation/air conditioning is limited.</p>		<p>The renewable energy requirement will trigger the evaluation of renewable energy supply systems which will also foster PV/BIPV deployment. Often it will be feasible to meet renewable electricity requirements by PV which would not foster BIPV deployment in the façades.</p> <p>The other requirements contribute to support PV/BIPV deployment but it can be expected that in general the requirements can usually be met by PV on the roof only.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: Little quantitative relevance for deployment of BIPV (in the façade)</p>

<p>Model rules for cantonal energy policy «MuKE n 2014»</p>	<p>Existing buildings: Standard solutions (SL): Replacing domestic hot water system: MuKE n 2014 provides a standard solution SL 7 (heat pump for hot water combined with PV) which requires a PV system with at least $5W_{peak}/m^2$ heated area.</p>	<p>If a proposed MuKE n 2014 standard solution (SL) is assessed, energy needs for heating and domestic hot water is assumed to be $100 kWh/m^2$</p>		<p>This fosters PV/BIPV deployment but the requirements can usually be met by PV on the roof only.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: Little quantitative relevance for BIPV (in the facade)</p>
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	Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
Model rules for cantonal energy policy «MuKE n 2014»				

Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
<p>Targets for renewable electricity generation in Switzerland in 2020 and 2035: The EnG defines targets for the years 2020 and 2035 for renewable electricity generation (except existing hydropower) in Switzerland 2020 at least 4'400 GWh/a and 2035 >14'500 GWh/a.</p>			<p>The targets contribute to foster future PV/BIPV deployment Quantitative relevance: Targets for 2020: Renewable electricity generation is supposed to be higher than 4'400 GWh/a and for 2035:>14'500 GWh/a</p>
<p>Article 25 of the Swiss Nature and Cultural Heritage Protection Act (Art. 25 NHG) which establishes one or more advisory federal commissions for nature conservation, cultural heritage protection and monument conservation :</p>	<p>According to Art. 16, Abs. 2, EnG, commissions and competence centres, established according to Article 25 of the Swiss Nature and Cultural Heritage Protection Act (Art. 25 NHG), have to elaborate expert assessments of projects within maximal 3 months.</p>	<p>Acceleration of approval processes for renewable energy: Cantons provide fast approval procedures for renewable energy deployment The Swiss federal council may designate an administrative unit which coordinates and supervises other approval and expert opinion procedures.</p>	<p>Art. 25 can accelerate and ease deployment of BIPV especially in urban centres as well as in rural areas and thereby contribute to remove obstacles for renewable energy deployment. Quantitative relevance: Low to at most moderate quantitative relevance, but it speeds up PV/BIPV deployment</p>
<p>Legal provision in the new energy law for the balancing of environmental/cultural and societal interests versus renewable energy related interests</p>		<p>Using existing potentials of renewable energies is declared to be in the national interest</p>	<p>Especially for larger renewable energy units as well as for units in urban areas this provision contributes to deployment of renewable energy units despite conflicts of interests. Quantitative relevance: Relevant quantitative impact on PV and BIPV deployment</p>

<p>(New) Swiss energy law EnG (version for the national referendum on 21.05.17)</p>	<p>Remuneration of electricity fed into the grid and One-off fee payments for PV/BIPV systems</p>	<p>If the capacity of the generating unit is less than 3 MW or 5'000 MWh/a, the local utilities have to accept feeding renewably generated electricity into their grid. They have to remunerate it adequately. The Swiss federal council may demand for minimal energy related, ecological or other requirements the producers have to comply with.</p> <p>On-site consumption of on-site generated electricity is allowed resulting in the substitution of electricity from the grid. This yields comparatively high cost savings.</p> <p>The feed-in remuneration program ends accepting new PV/BIPV units after 6 years.</p>	<p>In the future, new PV/BIPV units with a capacity of >100 kW_{peak} can still apply for subsidies by feed-in remuneration for a limited period of time (if funds are available). Existing funds for feed-in remuneration are allocated first to already registered projects, waiting for remuneration, which is why only few new applicants will be subsidized by feed in remuneration.</p> <p>Owners with BIPV/PV units >30kW_{peak} (according to EnFV) who are newly participating in the feed-in remuneration program, have to sell their production by themselves on the market.</p> <p>Feed-in tariffs are decreasing in the future, depending on the future costs of the most efficient new PV/BIPV units. The funds for feed-in remuneration are limited.</p> <p>Owners of new and of significantly extended PV/BIPV units can apply for one-off fee payments (in the maximum 30% of the investment costs of reference units) if funds are available.</p> <p>There will be one-off fee payments for small units (2-100 kW_{peak}) and large units (100 kW – 50 MW_{peak}) which will have differing waiting periods between registering for the subsidy and payment of the subsidy (about 3-4 years for small and 6-7 years for large units)</p>	<p>The feed-in remuneration yields limited additional future incentives for BIPV/PV deployment, since most of available funds are allocated to already waiting projects.</p> <p>Self-marketing of subsidized PV/BIPV electricity will decrease free running effects and bring resulting subsidies closer to market conditions and increases their efficiency. On the other hand, this will increase complexity and efforts for the feed-in tariff applicants which impedes the use of feed-in remuneration by PV/BIPV projects.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: Decreasing feed-in tariffs and future abandonment of feed-in remuneration have a high impact on PV/BIPV deployment. Impact on the more expensive BIPV systems might be higher, especially for façade systems.</p> <p>As off 2018, one-off fee payments will be the relevant PV/BIPV subsidy instrument. Expected waiting times for the subsidy will lower the effectiveness of this subsidy on PV/BIPV deployment.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: The provision of one-off fee payments is highly relevant. Its quantitative effects depend on the funding rate, the funds provided and the hampering effect of the expected waiting times for the payment of the subsidies.</p> <p>Currently 29'000 small units are on the waiting list, whereof 40% are already installed. For the future, >100 MW/a of large units applying for one-off fee payments are expected (SFOE, 24.03.2017).</p>
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Framework conditions, objectives		Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
(New) Swiss energy law EnG (version for the national referendum on 21.05.17)	Dissent on the remuneration of electricity fed into to the grid	If PV/BIPV system owners and the corresponding utility can't reach an agreement on the remuneration of fed-in electricity, the deliveries to the grid have to be remunerated according to the prices on the forward market for electricity, taking into account quality of the delivery, electricity demand and supply.		This measure ensures a lower limit for feed-in remunerations. It tends to increase BIPV/PV deployment independently from local energy suppliers. Quantitative relevance: Limited to the cases of dissent

Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
<p>Federal energy ordinance EnV (draft version for the currently ongoing consultation process; March 2017)</p>	<p>The EnV regulates grid connection of building with PV/BIPV electricity generation. This includes the obligation for the utility and grid owner to accept PV/BIPV-electricity fed-into the grid and to adequately remunerate such deliveries according to the cost savings incurred.</p>	<p>Using part of the PV/BIPV electricity generated on-site in the building (as well as in neighbouring buildings as long as the public grid is not used) is allowed as well as the constitution of a self-consumption collective using on-site generated electricity (Eigenverbrauchsgemeinschaft).</p>	<p>These regulations in the ordinance establish the conditions to feed in to the grid on-site generated electricity and to be remunerated adequately corresponding to the possible cost savings for the utility.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: Quantitative relevance is high and not depending on limited funds for subsidy programs. It will gain weight if smart meter and smart grid devices will allow for increasing the share of self-consumed electricity generated on-site.</p>
<p>Federal ordinance for energy subsidy programs EnFV (draft version, March 2017)</p>	<p>The EnFV defines notions like «integrated PV system» and «detached PV system» or large units (>100 kW_{peak}) and small units (<100 kW_{peak}).</p> <p>The grid charge for funding the subsidies according to Art. 35, Abs. 2a – Abs. 2j, comprising among others the funding of one-off fee payments, feed-in remunerations, is increased to 2.3 ct./kWh</p>	<p>(Future) owners of PV/BIPV systems with a capacity >30 kW_{peak} benefitting from feed-in remunerations have to market their PV/BIPV production by themselves. This holds also for present PV/BIPV owners of systems with a capacity >500 kW_{peak} benefitting already from feed-in remunerations</p>	<p>Self-marketing of subsidized PV/BIPV electricity will decrease free runner effects, increasing their efficiency and bring resulting subsidies closer to market conditions.</p> <p>Self-marketing could be an obstacle for the owners of the corresponding systems, tending to decrease the effectiveness of the subsidies provided as well as the propagation of PV/BIPV.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: The quantitative relevance is not clear and depends on the one hand on the complexity and necessary efforts for the self marketing. On the other hand it depends on the positive impact on the efficiency of the subsidy program, reducing free running.</p> <p>At the time being, the newly installed one-off fee payments accelerate BIPV/PV deployment since there is a long waiting list for feed-in remuneration applications and limited funds, limiting the access to subsidies by feed-in remunerations and hindering faster extension of PV/BIPV deployment.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: Quantitative relevance of higher funds for one-off fee payments is high (see above).</p>

	Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
<p>Minergie-standards 2017: Minergie-Minergie-P-Minergie-A--standard</p>	<p>The Minergie standards are established by the Minergie Association. The standards are accepted by several subsidy programs and for cantonal requirements in the building sector. The Minergie requirements address the operational energy needs of a building, i.e. the energy needs for heating, ventilation, air conditioning and cooling (HVAC), domestic hot water (DHW), lighting, appliances and building integrated technical systems (BITS) as well as renewable electricity generation on-site.</p>	<p>All Minergie standards: Requirements of the basic module of MuKE n with respect to heating energy needs of a building have to be fulfilled. → this ensures good/high efficiency of the building envelope</p> <p>The Minergie energy indicator value represents a target value for the net weighted energy consumption for operating the whole building, comprising energy needs for heating, ventilation, air conditioning and cooling (HVAC), domestic hot water (DHW), lighting, appliances and building integrated technical systems (BITS) minus the weighted on-site electricity generation. Thereby the share of on-site generation not used on-site but fed into the grid is weighted by 40% only.</p> <p>National (political) conversion factors for the different energy carriers (final energy) are used to appraise the compliance of the weighted energy use with the required target value of the Minergie indicator value for energy use (Minergie-Kennzahl). Electricity generation on-site as well as electricity deliveries from the grid are weighted by a factor $g_{el} = 2$.</p>		<p>Incentive to install PV/BIPV capacities to fulfil the particular Minergie standard. Furthermore, incentive to maximise on-site use of on-site generated electricity. But because of the conversion factor of 40% for fed back electricity the incentive to install PV/BIPV capacities that exceed the on-site needs decreases.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: Taking into account overall energy use in the building as well as on-site renewable electricity generation has a relevant quantitative impact on PV/BIPV deployment. In buildings with fossil energy in use the positive effect is smaller the higher the weighting factor for on-site generated electricity is.</p>
		<p>New buildings, all Minergie standards No non-renewable energy use for heating and domestic hot water. All new Minergie buildings have to generate on-site electricity from renewable sources. PV/BIPV: Generation capacity must be at least 10 W_{peak}/m^2 heated area (no need to install more than 30 kW_{peak} per building) (analogous to MuKE n 2014)</p> <p>If the required target value of the Minergie energy indicator value is undercut by at least 5 kWh/m^2a, there is no requirement to install on-site renewable electricity generation capacities.</p>		<p>These requirements foster PV/BIPV.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: The minimum requirement can generally already be met by PV on the roof only. Distinct incentive for BIPV-in the façades can only be expected in the case of larger buildings with limited roof area.</p> <p>This offers flexibility in the way the target value is achieved but it is negative for PV/BIPV deployment</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: Limited negative impact on PV and BIPV demand</p>
		<p>Minergie-A: Yearly electricity generation on-site has to cover at least the yearly operational energy consumption of the building.</p>		<p>Quantitative relevance: Very strong incentive to install PV and BIPV capacities, especially for larger buildings since PV on the roof only might not be enough to cover the yearly consumption.</p>

Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
<p>Plusenergy-Standard</p> <p>Definition by energie-cluster.ch</p> <p>and</p> <p>Definition by «Energy certificate for buildings» (Norm SIA 2031:2016)</p>	<p>The Plusenergy standard addresses the energy consumption of a building for HVAC, DHW, lighting, appliances and BITS as well as renewable electricity (energy) generation on-site.</p> <p>Definition of Plusenergy building according to energie-cluster.ch: Yearly overall operational energy consumption for HVAC, DHW, lighting, appliances and BITS is lower than yearly renewable energy generation on the building lot. There is no particular requirement concerning energy efficiency of the building envelope, in particular not for renovated buildings</p> <p>Plusenergy buildings according to SIA 2031:2016 (Swiss society of engineers and architects in «Energy certificate for buildings»): The yearly weighted energy consumption of HVAC, DHW, lighting, appliances and BITS (determined according to SIA 380) has to be less than the target value of SIA 2031:2016 (which complies with SIA 380/1 from 2009). Furthermore, the primary energy value according to SIA 2031:2016 must be negative and yearly heating energy needs according to SIA 380/1 is less than the target value $QH_{,ii}$ of SIA 380/1.</p>		<p>Fosters PV/BIPV on renovated buildings to compensate an inefficient envelope.</p> <p>Fosters PV/BIPV mainly on new buildings (since for renovated buildings the target value of SIA 380/1 is hard to comply with)</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: For PV highly relevant. For BIPV in façades primarily relevant for larger buildings (with limited roof area). The requirements of energie-cluster.ch will result in more BIPV in façades than the requirements of SIA, since the requirements of energie-cluster.ch regarding energy efficiency of the building envelope are less demanding and allow for compensating higher energy consumption by PV/BIPV production on the building..</p>
<p>Calculation-/conversion factors</p>	<p>Definition of Plusenergy according to energie-cluster.ch: National conversion factor of 2 for electricity generated by PV/BIPV as well as for electricity from the grid</p> <p>Definition according to SIA 2031:2016: LCA based primary energy conversion factors for the conversion from final to primary energy. Alternatively: National conversion factors.</p> <p>The primary energy conversion factors for electricity based on a life cycle assessment (also proposed in the methodology report of econcept for Active Interfaces) differ from the national conversion factor (national conversion factor $g_{el} = 2$, life cycle assessed factor for swiss consumer mix $g_{el} = 3.14$ for total primary energy use and for PV $g_{el} = 1.42$ for total primary energy use).</p>		<p>The lower the conversion factors for the electricity produced the more PV/BIPV capacities have to be installed to compensate for a given energy consumption.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance of the different definitions Limited quantitative relevance on BIPV deployment.</p>

	Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
<p>Federal tax law; amendment of Art. 32 (draft version for the currently ongoing consultation process)</p>	<p>The range of tax deductions allowed for energy and environment related building renovation investments is extended</p>		<p>Investment costs of building renovation measures increasing energy efficiency and deployment of renewable energy can be split on 2 tax periods following the execution of the measures and deducted from the taxed income in these periods.</p>	<p>Significant financial incentive to deploy PV/BIPV systems</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: Resulting possible tax reductions are financially very relevant so that a distinct fostering effect can be expected for BIPV and PV, leading to more extensive BIPV projects and therefore to more BIPV in the façades.</p>
<p>Federal law on spatial planning (RPG) and the federal spatial planning ordinance (RPV)</p>	<p>According to RPG Art. 18a and RPV Art. 32a Abs. 1a PV systems on the roof can be installed without a building permit if they surpass vertically the roof area not more than 20 cm, do not surpass the roof area (horizontally), are low reflecting (anti glare technique) and are a compact, contiguous and connected area. In these cases a simple notification procedure can be applied.</p> <p>BIPV systems in the façade (are not in the list for the simplified notification procedure according to Art. 32a RPV) as well as PV systems on cultural monuments and inventoried buildings of national or cantonal relevance need a building permit</p>	<p>The cantons can issue particular requirements for the installation of PV/BIPV which take into account local characteristics and specificities. But they are not supposed to restrict PV deployment more than the federal regulation and the requirements have to be specific and proportionate.</p> <p>PV/BIPV installations on cultural monuments and inventoried buildings are special cases. Nevertheless they are supposed to be approved if they do not impair these objects to a significant extent (Swissolar 2017).</p>	<p>Federal regulation notes that using solar energy is considered to have a higher relevance than aesthetic aspects (Swissolar 2017)</p>	<p>The attribution of a high interest on deploying PV/BIPV as well as the provision of a simplified notification procedure for well integrated and designed roof PV systems fosters deployment of PV systems. BIPV on the façade are not eligible for the simplified notification procedure.</p> <p>Quantitative relevance: The upgrade of PV/BIPV deployment when balancing differing interests will be quantitatively relevant in all cases with conflicts of interests.</p> <p>The simplified notification procedure might foster PV/BIPV deployment on the roof and smooth the way towards widespread deployment at least of roof integrated systems.</p>

Table 1 Overview of regulations, standards and labels significant for the installation of PV and BIPV systems and indications concerning their impact on PV/BIPV deployment

In the following subchapters we summaries per regulation, standard or label the central impacts on PV and BIPV.

2.2.3 Model rules for cantonal energy policy (MuKEEn 2014)

MuKEEn 2014 fosters PV or BIPV by the obligation for new buildings to produce some electricity on-site. The mandatory production capacity can mostly be covered by PV on the roof or by roof-integrated PV only. Since more complex BIPV in the façade is more expensive and generally yields less electricity output per m² than PV on the roof (added or integrated), it can be expected that it will only be chosen as a solution if this is needed to fulfil the minimum conditions. This might be the case if the building is large and the roof area is not large enough or not suitable to generate enough PV electricity, i.e. mainly in densely built areas.

MuKEEn does not allow compensating energy needs for heating and domestic hot water by PV/BIPV electricity generation.

MuKEEn 2014 supports PV/BIPV deployment within the renovation of existing buildings by requiring that maximal 90% of the energy demand is produced by non-renewable energy after replacement of the heating system as well as by offering one standard solution (S7) combining PV and a heat pump for hot water production to fulfil the requirement of a 10% share of renewable energy for covering the heating needs. Since this solution needs relatively little PV capacity it will hardly be an particular incentive to install BIPV on the façade.

2.2.4 Energy law (EnG) and corresponding federal ordinances (EnV, EnFV)

Thanks to the new Swiss energy law and the corresponding federal ordinances the grid charge to fund subsidies for renewable energy systems is increased. The resulting increase of the funds for subsidizing renewable energy use fosters also PV and BIPV deployment, since a relevant part of the fund will be dedicated to photovoltaic installations (one-off investment grants and feed-in remunerations).

The feed-in remuneration as a subsidy mechanism is becoming less and less attractive. There is a long waiting list, the program will run out until 2025 and the PV/BIPV owners benefitting from feed-in remuneration will have to market their energy production themselves (if the system has a capacity >30 kW). The share of funds from the grid charge allocated to feed-in remunerations helps to cut the currently existing project waiting list, but most probably it will not provide subsidies for new future PV/BIPV projects any more or only for a limited number of new projects.

Therefore, two other measures should foster PV/BIPV in the future:

- The one-off investment grants will be applicable for PV/BIPV installations with a capacity up to 50 MW_{peak}.
- Self-consumption, substituting delivered electricity and the corresponding costs as well as the establishment of self-consumption collectives are allowed and the corresponding

framework conditions are established. This means of fostering PV/BIPV deployment and maximising the share of self-consumed electricity will become more important the more demand side optimizing (cost-effective) smart meters and control devices will be available. This will also support BIPV deployment in the façade, since façade BIPV units have a different temporal (daily and seasonally) production profile than roof installations, allowing for timely optimization of BIPV electricity generation.

2.2.5 Minergie standards

In contrast to MuKE 2014 the Minergie standard allows to compensate operational energy consumption for HVAC, DHW, lighting and BITS by on-site electricity production consumed on-site or fed into the grid for the sake of achieving the required Minergie energy indicator value. This is an incentive to install more than the minimum of on-site electricity production capacities required by MuKE 2014. Since Minergie buildings have to fulfill high energy efficiency standards, there is usually not that much to compensate any more.

The requirements of the Minergie standard are based on yearly balances of operational energy demand and on-site renewable electricity generation. Thereby, only 40% of the electricity fed into the grid can be deducted from the building's energy needs according to the Minergie energy indicator value.

Only Minergie-A buildings have to compensate their entire yearly operational energy consumption by on-site energy production. Since PV on the available roof area might not produce enough electricity, façade-BIPV could become an important solution for Minergie-A buildings.

Since new Minergie buildings are not allowed to use fossil fuels any more, operational energy needs are mainly covered by electricity (heat pump, lighting, appliances, BITS etc.). Since demand for delivered electricity has to be compensated by on-site generated renewable electricity it does not matter, what level the conversion factor for electricity has, as long as there is just one factor for all kinds of electricity. The conversion factor would be relevant if fossil energy consumption had to be compensated by on-site electricity generation.

2.2.6 Plusenergy standard

Plusenergy according to energie-cluster

For energie-cluster there are generally speaking no explicit minimum requirements for the energy efficiency of the building envelope. But the requirement is that the yearly primary energy consumption of the building has to be smaller than the renewable energy production on the building site. The national conversion factor of 2 for electricity is applied on the yearly balance of electricity deliveries from the grid minus the electricity fed into the grid. The lower the conversion factor for the on-site produced electricity the harder it becomes to compensate the building's energy needs covered by non-renewable energy carriers. Consequently, lower conversion factors tend to lead to more PV/BIPV capacities installed to compensate non-renewable energy use.

Especially for older buildings Plusenergy according to energie-cluster is an interesting concept, since shortcomings of the envelope can be compensated by more energy production on-site.

2.2.7 Active Interfaces: Methodological frame-work

Within «Active Interfaces» (AI) some of the above mentioned aspects are treated in the paper «Common methodological frame-work to assess energy, climate and economic impacts of BIPV», (econcept 13.6.2016). The AI project teams are supposed to use this common methodological frame-work to assess the different BIPV solutions and compare them with solutions without BIPV.

Assessment components

Concerning the relevant energy use, the paper suggests the following:

«We assume that the assessments are carried out for entire buildings which are renovated, investigating the subsequent components of operational energy use and related GHG-emissions:

- Space heating, cooling and ventilation (HVAC)
- Domestic hot water (DHW)
- Auxiliary energy use for fans, pumps, electric valves, control devices etc.
- It is suggested not to include energy use for artificial lighting, built-in common appliances (like refrigerators, elevators etc.) and plug-in appliances (if they have to be included it is suggested to do so with the help of default values if no metered values are available (the INSPIRE calculation tool would provide default values)». (econcept 2016)

Plug-in appliances are not included either in the above analysed regulations, labels and standards. But lighting, built-in appliances and building integrated technical systems are part of the energy calculations in Minergie and in Plusenergy buildings. This is a slight variation of the proposition made for AI.

Conversion factors

Concerning the conversion factors, the paper states that life cycle assessed conversion factors are held appropriate.

«For the assessment of «Active Interfaces»-measures within building renovation, the national mix of electricity consumed is usually most appropriate (see Frischknecht, Itten, 2014: "CH-Verbrauchsmix", Table 2.1, p. 5) at least for determining primary energy impacts of electricity savings due to AI measures:

Primary energy factors PEF of electricity from the grid, Swiss consumption mix:

Total primary energy PEF_{tot} : 3.14 ($\triangleq g_{el}$)

Non-renewable primary energy PEF_{nr} : 2.68; (whereby PEF_{fossil} : 0.47 and $PEF_{nuclear}$: 2.21) »
(econcept 2016)

The LCA-based factor of the Swiss consumption mix is proposed also for electricity generated on-site by PV/BIPV-installations, because it replaces electricity that would have to be purchased otherwise from the grid.

The often used national conversion factor also stipulates a single primary energy conversion factor ($g_{el} = 2$) for electricity generated on-site and for electricity consumed.

Quite different is the valuation of on-site generated electricity stipulated by the norm SIA 380 («basis for energy calculation of buildings», SIA 380:2015) of the Swiss Society of Engineers and Architects (SIA). While it prescribes the use of specific primary energy factors for electricity consumed based on the origin of the electricity delivered, it prescribes different primary energy valuation factors for on-site generated electricity which is fed back into the grid: Fed back electricity is valued by its primary energy content, thereby including embodied energy of installing a PV system on the building (average $g_{elPV} = 1.42$, while g_{elPV} varies between 1.38 – 1.54, depending on the system and the kind of installation on the building). We consider this valuation as political valuation, not been appropriate, since fed back electricity substitutes electricity production from the grid and should be valued according to the conversion factor for the electricity mix substituted: In general, this is the conversion factor for the production mix of the electricity consumed in Switzerland (consumption mix). If the production mix of electricity distributed by the local provider is available, the conversion factor for this local production mix could be applied.

System boundaries

The system boundaries for the energy and GHG emissions related assessment of renovated buildings and the definition of the relevant energy flows according to the methodology paper in AI are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Definition of the levels and system boundaries of energy use in buildings being renovated, including on-site renewable energy generation, passive heat gains, exported energy and embodied energy for renovation measures (Kurnitski J., 2011, REHVA Task Force, supplemented by econcept)

«Net delivered energy» (dashed dark blue line in Figure 1) comprises energy carriers delivered to the building minus on-site generated energy exported from the building to the grid or to a heating/cooling energy distribution system. (econcept 2016)

The system boundaries of the above described labels and standards differ only slightly:

- MuKE 2014 does not allow to compensate energy delivered for heating and domestic hot water with on-site generated electricity and the export of electricity.
- Minergie only allows 40% of the yearly exports of on-site generated electricity to be deducted while calculation the energy indicator value.

2.2.8 Further possible impacts from changes in the framework conditions under discussion

Financing the power grid

The increase of decentralized electricity generation, e.g. by PV/BIPV capacities, raises the question of how to finance the existing grid, which will still be necessary also with increasing decentralized power production. The introduction of (or increase of possibly already existing) maximum demand rates (CHF/kW) is an option which is currently being discussed for charging the grid costs in the case of decreasing yearly energy demand (kWh/a) from the grid but remaining demand for power (kW) by decentralized prosumers. At the time being, the federal electricity supply ordinance (SR 734.71) restricts the extent to which grid costs are charged by maximum demand rates: it requires that the grid tariff for final consumers (supplied with <1kV) without existing metering of maximum demand has to be to at least 70% a non-degressive energy tariff.

→ Maximum demand rates are negative for PV/BIPV systems that have just become economically viable thanks to on-site self-consumption substituting consumption from the grid, since maximum demand rates would reduce financial benefits of self-consumption.

Remuneration of electricity fed back to the grid

For the time being, electricity fed back from decentralized producers into the grid is remunerated varyingly, often lowly, depending on the utility or grid owner and often not in accordance with the prescriptions of EnG and EnV. This indicates at least an implementation problem.

→ The current situation is unsatisfactory even though low feed-in remunerations foster measures to maximise self-consumption on-site as well as the installation of on-site storage capacities. But prosuming is economically hampered because of low feed-in remunerations for prosumers.

Metering costs and smart meters

Metering is a relevant cost issue. At least for systems with less than 100 kW sophisticated metering devices might act economically prohibitive and hamper PV/BIPV deployment economically.

Installation of storage capacities which is connected with the grid requires smart meters. In the near future it can be expected that the installation of smart meter will spread and perhaps even become mandatory which could decrease metering costs and increase the possibilities to optimize on-site electricity production and electricity demand.

2.2.9 Comment on allocation rules in the view of latest research results

The spreading use of energy assessments and evaluations on the primary energy level urge to use LCA-based conversion (weighting) factors to determine primary energy use depending on final energy use and depending on the chosen energy carriers. The different Swiss standards discussed above apply mostly national conversion factors. In the case of electricity the national conversion factor is distinctly smaller than the LCA-based average conversion factor for the electricity mix of electricity consumed in Switzerland ($g_{el} = 2$ instead of 2.68 for non-renewable and 3.14 for total primary energy use).

For buildings still using fossil energy carriers a low conversion factor makes it more difficult to compensate fossil energy use by PV/BIPV production since more capacity has to be installed. A higher conversion factor reduces the required capacities. For buildings using only electricity also for the heating needs, the conversion factor has no effect on the required on-site PV/BIPV capacities for the compensation since consumption and generation are weighted by the same conversion factor.

The scope of energy use (from energy use for heating and DHW only to the inclusion of energy use for ventilation, cooling, lighting, appliances, BITS and mobility) as well as the system boundaries of the regulations, standards and labels investigated matter for the deployment of BIPV/PV. Usually the more comprehensive the scope on the energy use in buildings is the more reasons urge for deploying PV/BIPV to meet the requirements of the particular standard or label.

2.2.10 Conclusions

Mandatory provisions and requirements like the requirement to install PV/BIPV capacities of at least $10 \text{ kW}_{\text{peak}}/\text{m}^2$ in new buildings or to have at least 10% renewable energy use in the case of the replacement of a heating system clearly foster deployment of renewable energy, especially of on-site generated PV/BIPV electricity.

Due to costs but also due to energy yields, most of the requirements for on-site renewable energy use or electricity generation facilitate PV deployment which will be first of all PV on the roof or PV integrated in the roof and only afterwards – if these capacities are not enough – BIPV in the façades.

BIPV deployment in façades is fostered by the Minergie-A and by the Plusenergie labels. So far these labels and their standards are voluntary and therefore, their impact on BIPV installations will be limited.

3 Situation in EU, Germany and Austria

To compare with and to possibly learn from other framework conditions for BIPV deployment, the situation on the level of the legislations of the European Union as well as the situation for BIPV in Germany and Austria are briefly outlined and assessed.

3.1 European Union

On the level of the EU legislation the impacts of the Energy Performance for Buildings Directive (EPBD), the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) and the Renewable Energy Directive (RED) on BIPV and PV deployment are considered.

EPBD focusses much on the energy performance of buildings (envelope and technical equipment) and the overall target of climate neutral buildings. Especially the latter requirement is an incentive to renewably generate on-site electricity.

By the definition of the nearly zero energy building (NZEB) and requiring that from 2021 (public buildings 2019) new buildings have to be NZEB, the EPBD establishes a strong incentive to deploy on-site renewable energy for complying with the NZEB-goal. This fosters PV as well as BIPV deployment. The EPBD applies a quite comprehensive scope with respect to the energy consumption in buildings, including also electricity consumption for non-heating use. This supports PV and BIPV deployment even more.

Besides the general provisions mentioned above, the EPBD has no specific incentives to foster BIPV in particular.

	Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
<p>EU: EPBD Energy Performance of Buildings Directive</p>	<p>Increasing the use of energy from renewable sources to 20% until 2020 and reduction of energy consumption by 20% in the Union to comply with the Kyoto Protocol of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), to reduce, by 2020, overall greenhouse gas emissions by at least 20% below 1990 levels, and by 30% in the event of an international agreement being reached.</p> <p>"Energy performance of a building" means the calculated or measured amount of energy needed to meet the energy demand associated with a typical use of the building, which includes energy used for heating, cooling, ventilation, hot water and lighting</p> <p>The current EPBD 2010 shall be revised, whereby the energy efficiency requirements for buildings shall be increased to comply with the more ambitious energy and climate policy targets for 2030.</p>	<p>EPBD requires that the member states establish energy related requirements for new buildings which corresponds to nearly zero energy buildings (NZEB), for public buildings as of 2019 and for non-public buildings until 2021.</p> <p>For major renovations of existing buildings corresponding requirements should be established at least for the renovated parts.</p> <p>EPBD lays down requirements as regards (EPBD Art. 1):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the common general framework for a methodology for calculating the integrated energy performance of buildings and building units; (b) the application of minimum requirements to the energy performance of new buildings and new building units; (c) the application of minimum requirements to the energy performance of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) existing buildings, building units and building elements that are subject to major renovation; (ii) building elements that form part of the building envelope and that have a significant impact on the energy performance of the building envelope when they are retrofitted or replaced; and (iii) technical building systems whenever they are installed, replaced or upgraded; 	<p>NZEB: "nearly zero-energy building" describes a building that has a very high energy performance, as determined in accordance with Annex I. The nearly zero or very low amount of energy required should be covered to a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources, including energy from renewable sources produced on-site or nearby (EPBD Art. 2).</p> <p>EPBD requirements address the overall energy consumption of the building, hence the requirements comprise also electricity consumption for non-heating use, which is favourable for PV/BIPV deployment on-site.</p> <p>The positive influence of on-site PV electricity generation can be taken into account to comply with the target (EPBD Annex 1).</p>	<p>The quantitative overall objectives are very relevant since they make far reaching efficiency improvements necessary as well as renewable energy deployment. The latter fosters PV and BIPV deployment.</p> <p>The quite comprehensive scope of energy use in the building whose non-renewable energy needs and GHG emissions have to be reduced, fosters the inclusion of renewable energy generation and thereby of PV and BIPV deployment.</p> <p>The NZEB definition explicitly opens the way to fulfil EPBD requirements by deploying renewable electricity generation to compensate for the remaining energy needs. Hence, efficiency improvements will usually be limited according to their economic efficiency compared to renewable energy deployment which becomes increasingly favourable with a better cost/benefit ratio of BIPV.</p> <p>Ambitious goals regarding mitigation of GHG and of non-renewable primary energy use support the deployment of BIPV.</p>

	Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
<p>EU: EED Energy Efficiency Directive</p>	<p>The EED pursues the overall . energy efficiency target of saving 20 % of the Union's primary energy consumption by 2020, and of making further energy efficiency improvements after 2020 (EED Art. 1 (10))</p> <p>Annex IV: Default primary energy factor for electricity of 2.5 (there are discussions about lowering the default factor to 2.0).</p>		<p>Priority access to the grid and dispatching of renewable electricity (as from PV/BIPV) Art. 15 (5)</p> <p>Promotion of energy services (Art. 18)</p>	<p>The impacts of the EED on PV/BIPV-deployment is limited to establishing a favourable context for PV/BIPV and where certain measures recommended (like fostering energy services) could also help PV/BIPV deployment.</p> <p>Lowering the primary energy factor for electricity increases the PV/BIPV-surface needed for compensating the remaining energy deliveries to the building.</p>

**EU: RED
Renewable En-
ergy Directive**

The RED establishes a common framework for the promotion of energy from renewable sources and sets mandatory national targets for the overall share of energy from renewable sources in gross final consumption of energy: at least 20% in 2020 and 27% in 2030 for the EU.

Each Member State had to adopt a national renewable energy action plan

Member States ensure that information on support measures is made available to all relevant actors, that information on the net benefits, cost and energy efficiency of equipment and systems for the use of heating, cooling and electricity from renewable energy sources is made available, that certification schemes or equivalent qualification schemes are available and provide public information on certification schemes, lists of qualified/certified installers and guidelines for planners and architects..

Member States ensure that transmission and distribution system operators in their territory guarantee transmission and distribution of electricity produced from renewable energy sources;

Member States shall also provide for either priority access or guaranteed access to the grid-system of electricity produced from renewable energy sources

When dispatching, transmission system operators have to give priority to generating installations using renewable energy sources as far as the secure operation of the national electricity system permits and based on transparent and non-discriminatory criteria (Art. 16)

Member States ensure that tariffs charged by transmission and distribution system operators for the transmission and distribution of electricity from plants using renewable energy sources reflect the real costs and benefits resulting from the plant's connection to the network (Art. 16)

The 20%/27% objectives for the share of renewable energy generation 2020/2030 and the obligation for the member states to elaborate national action plans foster renewable energy in general as well as PV and BIPV.

The numerous measures to support renewable energy and PV/BIPV deployment outlined in the RED can help to establish favourable framework conditions for deployment of PV and BIPV and for marketing their electricity generation either by self-consumption or by feeding back into the grid.

Each member state decides on its national framework conditions and the regulations providing a favourable setting for PV/BIPV deployment.

Table 2 Overview of EU regulations relevant for the installation of PV and BIPV systems and indications concerning their impact on PV/BIPV deployment

3.2 Germany

In Germany several regulations, federal concepts and initiatives influence the energy performance of buildings, energy use in buildings and (on-site) energy generation in buildings.

Subsequently, the following federal regulations are considered, further regulations of German states are not taken into account:

- EnEG 2013: Energy Conservation in Buildings Law
- EnEV 2014: Energy Conservation Ordinance
- EEG 2017: Renewable Energy Law
- EEWärmeG: Law regarding the promotion of renewable energy use for heating, domestic hot water and cooling in buildings
- Energy Concept of the Federal German Government

Past success in PV-deployment in Germany is based mainly on the rather generous subsidies resulting from the feed-in remuneration guaranteed to PV-installers.

Impact on PV-deployment from the existing German regulatory framework conditions besides the feed-in remunerations can be expected from the objective to require as of 2021 a nearly zero energy buildings standard (with respect to primary energy parameters) for new buildings as well as more energy related renewal of existing buildings leading to a nearly zero energy building stock in 2050 (herewith, Germany is implementing the objectives of the EU-EPBD).

There is no special attention to BIPV in the objectives, regulations and concepts considered.

	Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
<p>EnEG 2013 Energy Conservation in Buildings Law</p>	<p>Scope: Heating, domestic hot water, ventilation, cooling, lighting. Nearly zero energy building as of 2021 (2019 for public buildings)</p>	<p>Scope of the EnEG: Primary energy needs for heating, domestic hot water, ventilation, cooling and lighting.</p>		<p>EnEG deals mainly with the energy demand for heating, domestic hot water and cooling. But the inclusion of lighting shifts the focus also on the electricity consumption of buildings such that on-site renewable electricity generation by PV/BIPV becomes a measure to reduce non-renewable primary energy consumption of buildings.</p> <p>The objectives are in line with the objectives of the EPBD</p>
<p>EnEV 2014 Energy Conservation Ordinance</p>	<p>Further development of EnEV2012 towards the objectives of the EPBD (NZEB-standard for new buildings) until 2020 and tightening of the requirements for existing buildings as far as economically viable.</p> <p>Long term goal: Nearly climate neutral building stock until 2050 (EnEV §1). Energy efficiency goals of EnEV 2014 for new buildings have been tightened 2016: Primary energy needs of the building was lowered by 25% compared to EnEV 2014.</p>	<p>Scope of the EnEV: Primary energy needs for heating, domestic hot water, ventilation, cooling and lighting.</p> <p>Electricity consumption from renewable sources can be deducted from the energy needs of the building to comply with the energy demand requirements (EnEV §5).</p>		<p>EnEV explicitly allows for deducting renewable energy generation from the needs of the building.</p> <p>Furthermore, EnEV defines a long term goal for existing buildings (2050) which creates opportunities for on-site renewable electricity generation with PV/BIPV to reduces energy demand relevant to comply with existing regulatory requirements.</p>

Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
<p>EEG 2017: Increase of the share of renewable electricity consumed to 40-45% until 2025, 55% - 60% until 2035 and to 80% until 2050 (EEG §1).</p> <p>Renewable Energy Law</p>	<p>PV installations >30 kW_{peak} have to allow for remotely influencing feed-into the grid by the grid operator, according to the grid load.</p> <p>The remuneration for PV-electricity is 8.91 €ct./kWh (since 01.02.2017; EEG §48, §49) and decreases every month by a certain percentage, depending on the capacity of newly installed PV/BIPV-units.</p> <p>Self-consumed PV/BIPV-electricity has to be metered.</p> <p>The EEG grid-apportionment has to be reimbursed for self-consumed on-site generated PV/BIPV-electricity.</p>	<p>Since 2014 reduction of subsidies for PV/BIPV electricity generation.</p> <p>Feed-in priority for PV/BIPV electricity but integration of PV/BIPV electricity into grid management and remote control whereby possible revenues passed are reimbursed by 95-100% to the PV-owners. (EEG §8, §9, §15).</p> <p>Market premium for owners of PV installations which can be remotely controlled and who market their electricity production themselves (EEG §15, §19, §20, §21, §22).</p> <p>Feed-in remuneration and remuneration for feed-in from multi-family tenant dwellings <100 kW_{peak}.</p> <p>Tendering of generation capacities for installations >100 kW_{peak}, which then are not allowed to self-consuming their production.</p>	<p>The generous feed-in remunerations for PV, which showed to be very successful with respect to PV deployment, have been reduced since 2014 and will be further reduced in the future.</p> <p>The need for self-marketing of subsidized PV-capacities and of participating in tendering procedures to apply for subsidies for larger installations reduces the fostering impact of remaining subsidies on new PV/BIPV deployment..</p>
<p>Energy Concept of the Federal German Government</p> <p>Climate neutral new buildings as of 2020, based on primary energy parameters and nearly climate neutral existing buildings until 2050.</p>	<p>New buildings as of 2021: Climate neutral new buildings based on primary energy indicators</p> <p>Existing buildings until 2050, primary energy indicators: Nearly 0%.</p> <p>Buildings in general until 2050: Primary energy use 50% and electricity use 75% compared to 2008</p>		<p>The energy concept specifies the objectives of EnEG and EnEV. The focus on strongly reducing primary energy demand parameters in the building sector should have a fostering impact on PV-deployment, even if the impact is indirect.</p>

	Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
EEWärmeG Law regarding the promotion of renewable energy use for heating, domestic hot water and cooling in buildings	Objective for 2020: A share of 14% for renewable energy on the final energy use for heating, domestic hot water and cooling (EEWärmeG §1).	New buildings (>50 m ²) have to cover the energy needs for heating and cooling partly by renewable energy (EEWärmeG §3). If solar energy is used to comply with the requirements, the share of solar energy covering energy demand for heating and cooling must be at least 15%.	EEWärmeG lists only solar thermal as renewable energy in the sense of EEWärmeG §3, but not PV-electricity. EEWärmeG subsidizes solar thermal and biogas heatings as well as heat pumps, but not PV.	It is not clear if PV-capacities are accepted as renewable energy in the sense of the EEWärmeG to meet the requirement of a 15% renewable energy share on the heating and cooling demand.

Table 3 Overview of German federal regulations relevant for the installation of PV and BIPV systems and indications concerning their impact on PV/BIPV deployment

3.3 Austria

Although Austria (especially Vorarlberg) is a pioneer with respect to solar architecture, demonstrating with path-breaking buildings that building integrated PV and solar thermal may result in convincing architectural solutions, there is little regulation and promotion with respect to PV and BIPV on the national level which is investigated in this report.

Based on the ÖSG (Law on the Promotion of Ecologically Generated Electricity) and with the help of the Austrian Climate and Energy Fund, deployment of new PV systems is subsidized.

Energy efficiency goals of EEEffG (Austrian Energy Efficiency Law) and the provisions in EEEffG Appendix 1h foster on-site PV/BIPV deployment in buildings to meet the required end-energy efficiency targets (determined on the basis of end-energy delivered to the building).

There are no provisions or measures to foster especially building and façade integrated PV systems.

	Framework conditions, objectives	Requirements	Measures fostering/hindering BIPV	Relevance for BIPV deployment
ÖSG 2012 Law on Ecological Electricity	Promotion of ecologically generated electricity. Goal 2010-2020: Increase of installed PV-capacity by +1'200 MW.		Two subsidy programs: Feed-in remuneration for 5 kW _{peak} < PV < 500 kW _{peak} (ÖSG §12) and subsidies for other PV systems (ÖSG §13). Investment grants for (the first) 5 kW _{peak} of PV systems; Climate and Energy Fund.	General promotion of PV deployment by the subsidies offered, but no particular incentives for BIPV.
EEffG 2014 Energy Efficiency Law	Increase of energy efficiency in Austria by about 20% from 2014 to 2020 to meet a quantitative target for end energy consumption in 2020.	On-site generated PV-electricity is contributing to reduce demand for delivered end-energy (EEffG Appendix 1h).		Increases the incentive to deploy PV in a general manner.

Table 4 Overview of Austrian federal regulations relevant for the installation of PV and BIPV systems and indications concerning their impact on PV/BIPV deployment

4 Concluding remarks regarding PV/BIPV in Switzerland and Europe

The analysis of the regulations, standards and labels on the level of the EU as well as on the federal level in Switzerland, Germany and Austria can be summarized as follows:

- The EU target of having as of 2021 for newly constructed buildings only nearly zero energy buildings (NZEB), to decrease correspondingly energy demand of existing buildings within major renovations and to cover the remaining energy needs of buildings to a substantial amount by renewable energy, fosters deployment of PV as well as of BIPV.
- The fact that the NZEB requirements are based on yearly balances for the energy needs of the building and for the compensation by on-site renewable energy production is as well fostering PV and BIPV deployment.
- The framework conditions investigated in Switzerland, Germany, Austria and on the EU level do not provide particular provisions or supporting measures for building integrated PV installations other than for PV in general.
- The investigated PV related subsidy programs and measures on EU level, in Germany and Austria do not favour building integrated PV compared to PV nor do they offer higher subsidies for BIPV.

In the EU as well as in Switzerland we can recognize increasing attention on climate protection and greenhouse gas mitigation targets:

- In Switzerland further development of the model rules for Cantonal energy policy (MuKE) by the conference of the cantonal energy councillors (EnDK) will go towards climate neutral building requirements.
- The new energy concept of the German federal government is also fostering the approach of climate neutral buildings
- The nearly zero energy approach of the EU-EPBD also aims towards climate neutral buildings: The requirement that the nearly zero or very low amount of energy required by the building should be covered to a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources, including energy from renewable sources produced on-site or nearby (EPBD Art. 2) delivers almost zero greenhouse gas emissions buildings.

In the building sector this leads to a certain shift of focus from currently prevailing energy conservation and efficiency improvements towards more extensively exploiting existing potentials for renewable energy deployment to further decrease greenhouse gas emissions of buildings. This reflects the increase of urgency which is attributed to climate protection. Therefore, the target of climate neutrality of buildings should be prioritised in the future. This will open the range of technical and economical options to further improve buildings towards sustainability, thereby contributing to mitigate the most urgent environmental and

resource problems. A future shift of policy priorities towards climate neutral will foster PV and BIPV deployment.

It is advantageous to base future energy and climate protection policy measures on targets which have to be met and not on particular technical solutions. With regard to BIPV and PV deployment this means that the share of BIPV on overall PV deployment will primarily be a result of the techno-economic viability of BIPV. Within this logic, higher subsidies for BIPV than for PV are not expedient.

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